

ATTRIBUTES OF MIDDLE-LEVEL MANAGERS IN THE PHILIPPINES HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The middle management is at a unique position of actualizing change in organizations. Middle-level managers simply need to be brought on board for any meaningful change to happen. It cannot be repudiated, that great success in an organization is mostly attributed to the remarkable and meaningful involvement of the low-profile middle-level managers of today. Their unique position in the management ladder greatly concretizes positive change in their sphere of influences. They should be valued for what they contribute because they have access to the top management and they can command the loyalty of the regular employees. Hence, any organizational leadership initiative for middle - level managers have to necessarily consider the importance of the middle management in the larger scheme of things. For these reasons, the study aimed to describe attributes of middle-level managers in selected higher education institutions in the Philippines and how these attributes jive with their leadership aspiration and potentials. The study used descriptive research design which involved quantitative and qualitative methods in gathering data. A validated self-made questionnaire, documentary analysis, focus group discussion and unstructured interview were utilized to gather the empirical data required. The subjects of the study were the 207 middle-level managers from 31 different HEIs in Batangas province. Random sampling was applied in determining the middle-level managers, and purposive sampling with equal distribution from each higher education institution was utilized to select the middle-level manager respondents. Frequency, percentage, and weighted mean were used as statistical treatment and analysis of data. Results showed that majority of the middle-level managers were female, belong to age group of 30 -39 years old, holding the position of a coordinator and have a master's degree. Moreover, most of them had 6-10 years of service as middle-level manager. The study recommended that the other variables like technological competence and parallel studies may be conducted. Other studies that may improve the leadership of middle-level managers may also be conducted.

Keywords: middle level managers, higher education, management ladder, organizational leadership